

CLIMATE CHANGE, HYDROLOGICAL VARIABILITY, AND AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN PUNJAB: A FMOLS-BASED EMPIRICAL ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

Climate change poses a growing threat to Pakistan's agricultural sector, particularly in Punjab, where temperature rise, erratic rainfall, and shifting hydrological patterns increasingly effect crop productivity. This study examines long-term climatic trends, temperature (1901-2020), rainfall (1901-2017), glacier melt indicators, and seasonal river flows and evaluates their economic impacts on major crops across North, Central, and South Punjab using the Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) model. Results reveal a consistent warming trend, increasing rainfall variability, accelerated glacier melt, and significant seasonal fluctuation in river discharge. FMOLS findings indicate that maximum temperature exerts strong negative effects on wheat, maize, and cotton yields, whereas minimum temperature, rainfall, and fertilizer use show region and crop specific impacts. Cultivated area remains a consistently positive determinant across all regions. These climatic stresses threaten food security and long-term agricultural sustainability. Region-specific adaptation strategies such as climate resilient crop varieties, improved irrigation efficiency, and enhanced hydrometeorological monitoring are essential to strengthen climate resilient in Punjab's agricultural systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate Change has emerged as one of the most profound challenges confronting agricultural systems across the world. Rising temperatures, altered precipitation patterns, increasing frequency of extreme weather events, and shifts in hydrological cycles are reshaping the productivity and sustainability of farming sectors, particularly in developing countries (IPCC, 2021-2022; Lobell et al., 2011). Agriculture in Pakistan contributing over 22 percent to the national GDP and

employing nearly two-fifth of the Labour force-remains highly climate-sensitive due to its dependence on natural climate-sensitive due to its dependence on natural climatic conditions, surface water availability, and traditional cropping practices (Hanif et al., 2010). Within Pakistan, the province of Punjab holds a central position, accounting for the largest share of national agricultural output, irrigated land, and rural population. However, its unique agro-ecological zones,

ranging from the barani (rainfed) Potohar plateau to the fertile canal-irrigated plains of central and southern Punjab, face diverse and intensifying climate-related stresses (Chaudhary & Rasul, 2011).

Over the past two decades, Punjab has experienced significant climatic variability, including rising mean temperatures, erratic monsoon behaviour, recurrent drought spells, smog formation, and severe flooding events along the Indus and its tributaries (Rasul & Chaudhary, 2010). These shifts have exerted measurable economic consequences: reduced crop yields, lower water-use efficiency, heightened vulnerability to pest and diseases, and escalating production costs (Ahmad et al., 2020; Baig & Ghauri, 2016). Major crops such as wheat, rice, maize, and cotton—pillars of Punjab's agricultural economy—have shown fluctuating productivity trends linked to climatic anomalies. Smallholder farmers, who constitute the majority of the farming community, are disproportionately affected due to limited adaptive capacity, financial constraints, and restricted access to climate-resilient technologies (Mahmood et al., 2019; Schlenker & Roberts, 2009).

Despite the growing body of global and national literature on climate-agriculture linkages, empirical evidence focusing specifically on Punjab remains limited, fragmented, or methodologically outdated. This research study aims to empirically examine the economic impacts of climate change on agriculture in Punjab by integrating climate indicators (temperature, rainfall, humidity, extreme events) with agricultural performance metrics. Through rigorous econometric analysis and spatial interpretation, the study seeks to provide evidence-based insights for policy planners, researchers, and development practitioners, ultimately contributing to a more resilient and sustainable agricultural sector in Punjab.

2. Methodology

2.1 To quantify the economic impacts of CC on melting of glaciers

Pakistan situated on crossroads of Western

Asia and Central Asia in South Asia. It is a federal parliamentary republic state. According to the populations it is 6th most populous country and its populations is more than 200 million. And according to the area it ranked at 36th largest country among the world. Its covering area is 881,913 sq (in square miles it is 340,509). Pakistan has a coastline along Arabian sea which length has 1,046 Km and in south there is a Oman in east which is surrounded by India. In west there is a Afghanistan, in southwest there is a Iran and in far northeast China (Qamar-uz-Zaman, 2009).

Pakistan owned some largest and longest glaciers among the world on Earth which has an estimated 15,000km² area. There is need and necessary to studied a space and field base glaciers which elaborate the role of glaciers for providing a water for agriculture and irrigation, and its role in geo dynamics and its sensitivity regarding to change in the climate. (M. Akhtar, 2008)

2.2 First Component: Trend Analysis (Christian Kroll, 2015) to identify increasing or decreasing patterns of Water Flow in Rivers.

i. Collected time-series data (1994-95–2023-24) for river discharge.

ii. Calculated changes in seasonal river flows.

2.3 Second components: The FMOLS estimator (Phillips & Hansen, 1990) was applied to examine long-run relationships between climate variables (temperature, rainfall), input variables (land area, fertilizer), and crop output across Punjab's three agroecological regions. This approach corrects for serial correlation and endogeneity, making it suitable for long-run climate yield assessments (Nelson et al., 2009; Schlenker & Roberts, 2009).

Crop Productivity

$$= f(Temp, RF, LA, UoF, WA)$$

Model Specification:

$$CropProd_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 * Temp_{it} + \beta_2 * RF_{it} + \beta_3 * LA_{it} + \beta_4 * UoF_{it} + \beta_5 * WA_{it} + \epsilon_{it}$$

Where:

CropProd → Crop productivity

(Dependent Variable)

Temp → Average temperature

RF → Rainfall

LA → Land area under cultivation

UoF → Use of fertilizers

WA → Water availability (from glacier melt)

ϵ → Error term

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Change in Annual Temperature of Pakistan

In the previous century, average global surface temperature has increased by approximately 0.074°C to 0.018°C. However, in last three decades, rate of variation has

accelerated ranging between 0.17°C and 0.052°C was observed (Trenberth et al., 2007). Regional climate change assessments typically rely on time series data of daily temperatures; however, challenges such as data gaps and inconsistent observation periods often limit the accuracy of such analysis. Similarly, in Pakistan, data of daily temperatures is not of that quality and consistency. So, an average surface temperature has been taken which has been increased during previous century. The annual time series data for time period (1901-2020) has been used to measure change in temperature of Pakistan.

Figure 3.1: Annual average temperature of Pakistan

Figure 3.1 shows the trend of Annual Average Temperature of Pakistan for the years 1901 to 2020. This shows increasing trend which means, average temperature is rising. There are certain reasons of the rise in temperature. These include human activities i.e., cutting and burning of trees, fossil fuels etc. Recently, Pakistan has experienced a higher variation in temperature resulting into erratic monsoon period leading to adverse flooding. So, the finding of this research study is similar with Chaudhary & Rasul (2011).

3.2 Change in Annual Rainfall of Pakistan

Pakistan lies in the western part of South

Asia between 24-37°N latitudes and 62-75°E longitudes. Rising temperatures and their influence on the atmosphere and rain are now apparent across all regions. The main factor of the climate variations is alterations in the rainfall patterns. Changes in the rainfall patterns directly affect water, agriculture and economy of the country. In recent decades, rainfall in many parts of Pakistan has become increasingly unreliable and unpredictable, intensifying the challenges for sustainable development. In this study, data of average annual rainfall for time period 1901 to 2017 has been taken and analyzed below.

Figure 3.2: Average annual rainfall in Pakistan

Figure 3.2 shows trend of average annual rainfall in Pakistan. It is depicted that; rainfall patterns are so erratic in the country. The variability of rainfall occurrence has been increased geographically.

Climate change means rising temperature along the time period, erratic patterns of rainfall, sea level rise and change in annual water flow in the rivers. When temperature rises, snow on glaciers starts to melt down, ultimately water flow increases in the rivers. This can be shown below through figures.

3.3 Impact of Climate Change on Melting of Glaciers

3.3.1 Annual Water Flow (MAF) in Rivers of Pakistan

3.3.1.1 Indus river

Figure 4.3: Annual flow of water in Indus River at Tarbela

Figure 4.3 shows trends of annual water in River Indus available at Tarbela. It is the longest river originating from Himalayan region. Ranked as the 21st longest river in world by annual discharge. Indus is the principal source of Pakistan’s water supply and serves as the backbone of its agriculture sector. Its major tributaries include the Kabul, Gilgit, Astore, Tanubal and Zanskar River.

1976-77 to 2022-23 is used for analysis. This figure shows 2 lines, blue line shows water available in Kharif season. Which shows that, in Kharif season, when temperature is rising, glacier’s melting rate is high so the water level is also high. Whereas, red line shows water available in Rabi season. Rabi season generally called as winter season. In northern areas of Pakistan, winter season has ice and snowfall, so there is less water in Rabi season.

Secondary data of Annual flow of water for

Figure 4.4: Indus at Kalabagh

Figure 4.4 shows annual flow of water in MAF from 1976-77 to 2022-23 in Indus River at Kalabagh. Blue line shows water level in Indus in Kharif season which shows erratic patterns. In certain years, water level is so low whereas, in some years, it is quite high. It ranges from 50 MAF to 90 MAF in

Kharif season. Red line is consistent, water level ranges 10 to 20 MAF during the same time period i.e., 1976-77 to 2022-23. Reason behind this low level of water is winter season. During winter season, there is snow on glaciers, so water level is low in Indus River.

Figure 4.5: Kabul at Nowshehra

3.3.1.2 River Kabul

Figure 4.5 above shows annual flow of water level in Kabul River at Nowshehra. This shows trend of water level for time period 1976-77 to 2022-23. Kabul river is basically 700 km long tributary of Indus River. It empties into the Indus near district Attock, which passes through Peshawar, Charsadda and Nowshehra. Data has been taken at Nowshehra. Blue line in the figure above shows water level in Kharif season where

snows melt and water level increases. Whereas, red line shows water level in Rabi season when there is snow on Hindukush range in winter season. Kharif shows water level ranges from 10 to 30 MAF. The highest level of water was in the year 1991-92, where temperature in figure 4.1 also shows the maximum temperature in same year. That shows melting of glacier in Kharif season.

Figure 4.6: Jhelum at Mangla

3.3.1.3 River Jhelum

Figure 4.6 shows annual flow of water in Jhelum River for time periods 1976-77 to 2022-23 at Mangla. This river is about 774 km long. It is among western rivers of Pakistan, merges with Indus at Kot Mathan. In the figure above, blue line higher than the red line, which shows water level in Kharif season in Pakistan. It shows large variation in water level during the time period. In the year 1994-95 water level is at lowest whereas, 1991-92 and 1997 shows water level at highest. High level of water shows rise in

temperature whereas, reason behind the low level of water is slow melting of glacier or low temperature during dry season. Red line below in the figure shows water level in Rabi season. Water level in Rabi season is quite low, which means, water availability for agriculture is less in Rabi than that of Kharif. The hydrology of the Jhelum River is mainly dependent on the snowmelt from the Karakoram and Himalaya ranges. Monsoon on the Indian subcontinent, brings heavy rains in summers.

Figure 4.7: Chenab at Marala

3.3.1.4 River Chenab

Figure 4.7 depicts annual water level in river Chenab at Marala MAF for the time period 1976-77 to 2022-23. Chenab river is among the five major rivers originates from Himalayas and streams through Jammu & Kashmir then merged with the Jhelum at Trimmu, combined with the Sutle. River

Chenab is approximately 960 km long. Blue line in figure above shows water level in Kharif season in river Chenab. This line shows large variations in water level that shows large variations in temperature in this time period. When temperature changes, snow cover melts and water flow increase in the rivers. Whereas, red line below in the

figure 4.7 shows water level in Rabi season. The water of Chenab River was assigned to Pakistan according to the terms of Indus Water Treaty in 1960. This water is

extensively used in Pakistan for agriculture and irrigation purpose. Its water is transferred to river Ravi through various link canals in Punjab.

Figure 4.8: Ravi at Balloki

3.3.1.5 River Ravi

Figure 4.8 above shows Annual water level in river Ravi at Balloki for time period 1976-77 to 2022-23. Ravi originates from Himalayas. It is transboundary river crossing North India and eastern Pakistan. In 1960, Indus Water Treaty allocates water of Ravi to India. Water flows 720 km through Indus River and merges with Arabian sea. In figure 4.8, blue line shows annual water level

during time period 1976-2019. This trend shows erratic patterns from 1976 to 2000 but then this water level has decreased. Red line shows water level in Rabi season. After year 2000, water level in Kharif and Rabi is almost equal. Reason of this low level of water is the construction of dams by India. Water is used by India and low level of water is drained in Ravi River for Pakistan.

Figure 4.9: Sutlej at Sulemanki

3.3.1.6 River Sutlej

Figure 4.9 above shows annual water level in river Sutlej at Sulemanki for time 1976-77 to 2022-23. Blue line reflects water level in Kharif whereas red line shows water in Rabi season. Sutlej river has almost dried because its water has been assigned to India according to Indus Waters Treaty 196, and then water is diverted for irrigation purpose. Sutlej river flows through the historic crossed

Punjab in India and Pakistan. Further, It is located in the south of the HKH segment of the Himalayas and east of the central Sulaiman Range, which is 550 km long.

3.4 Impact of Melting of glaciers on agricultural production

Province Punjab mainly depends on canal water (especially from the Indus basin) for its irrigation purpose. Canal water comes from the rivers which comes from glaciers in

Himalayas, Karakoram, and Hindukush region (New Lines magazine, 2025). Glaciers in Pakistan are like natural water storage. They accumulate snow in the Rabi season and melt in Kharif season, river water flow rises and this water is available for use when rainfall is less reliable (Khan. A., 2025). Accelerated glaciers melt increases earlier runoff in the season, which can increase the risk of floods, and (GLOFs). However, later in the season, water availability may decline more rapidly which leads to water stress or scarcity (K. Saleem., 2025). Water crises will lead to crop losses, farmer income decline so the food security is at higher risk in Punjab, Pakistan.

In this research study, impact of climate variation on agricultural production has been

3.4.1.1 Wheat production model

The wheat production model analyzed the impact of rainfall, maximum temperature, minimum temperature,

analyzed on the basis of regions. Punjab has been divided into North, Central and South Punjab.

3.4.1 North Punjab

North Punjab is characterized by rain-fed agriculture, highly depending on rainfall, vulnerability to climate change, strong reliance on wheat, groundnut and maize production. In this study, three districts Rawalpindi, Jhelum and Chakwal were included. Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square Regression has been applied to analyze long-run relationship of rainfall, Maximum Temperature, Minimum Temperature, use of fertilizer, land area available for production and water available to the different crops.

fertilizer use, and cultivated area by using FMOLS estimation technique. The results are given below:

Table 4.3: Wheat production in north Punjab

Variables	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Rainfall	0.177	0.997	0.321
Maximum temperature	-10.247	-2.027	0.045
Minimum temperature	8.358	1.918	0.058
Fertilizer use	25.753	0.175	0.861
Cultivated area	0.379	2.649	0.0097

Results in the above table show that Rainfall has positive statistically effect showing precipitation does not drive wheat yield. A one degree increase in maximum temperature will result in decrease in wheat yield in north Punjab. Minimum temperature is slightly positive significant to wheat yield. Fertilizer use shows an

3.4.1.2 Rice production model

The rice production model used FMOLS to estimate the impact of rainfall, temperature

insignificant effect which indicates input inefficiency or limited response to wheat production. Overall, wheat production is most vulnerable to higher maximum temperatures, while cultivated area expansion is the highly significant and fertilizer effectiveness is limited.

variations, use of fertilizer and area on the rice in Northern Punjab. Results are given below:

Table 4.4: Rice production in north Punjab

Variable	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Rainfall	0.011	2.551	0.017

Maximum temperature	0.026	0.239	0.8131
Minimum temperature	-0.190	-1.321	0.198
Fertilizer use	-0.006	-0.165	0.870
Cultivated area	1.167	17.084	0.000

Results in the above table show that rainfall has a positive, significant effect. Which highlights that rice yield is strongly dependent on water availability. Maximum Temperature is insignificant, suggesting that extreme temperature is less critical for rice than for wheat. Minimum temperature has negative but insignificant effect on rice yield. Similarly, fertilizer use is insignificant, implying low responsiveness of rice production to additional use of fertilizer.

Table 4.5: Maize production in north Punjab

Variable	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Rainfall	0.011951	2.551264	0.0175
Maximum temperature	0.026898	0.239101	0.8131
Minimum temperature	-0.190287	-1.321740	0.1987
Fertilizer use	-0.006482	-0.165123	0.8702
Cultivated area	1.167524	17.08461	0.0000

In the table above, Rainfall has a negative but insignificant effect. Maximum temperature significantly reduces maize yields, which confirms vulnerability to heat stress. Minimum temperature is positive but insignificant to maize production. Cultivated area and fertilizer use both have positive highly significant impact on maize yield. Overall, maize production is strongly influenced by maximum temperature, fertilizer use, and cultivated area, while rainfall plays minor role.

3.4.2 Central Punjab

Central Punjab forms the agricultural backbone of Pakistan due to its fertile land, intensive irrigation and high crop

Overall, rice production in North Punjab is highly dependent on Rainfall, and cultivated area while fertilizer and temperature play minor roles.

3.4.1.3 Maize production model

The maize production model focused and examined rainfall, temperature variability cultivated area and fertilizer use by using FMOLS estimation technique. Results are presented below:

productivity. Three districts Lahore, Faisalabad and Sialkot from the central region were selected for the analysis of crop production. The Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square results for wheat, rice, and maze are presented below, with a detailed interpretation for each variable.

3.4.2.1 Wheat production model

Fully Modified OLS regression for production of wheat in North Punjab shows that minimum temperature, fertilizer usage, and cultivated area have significant positive impacts, whereas canal water availability negatively affects productivity. Rainfall and maximum temperature are statistically insignificant in this region.

Table 4.6: Wheat production in central Punjab

Variable	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Rainfall	0.298	0.854	0.395
Maximum temperature	-6.863	-0.813	0.419
Minimum temperature	59.715	6.641	0.000
Fertilizer use	653.026	4.434	0.000

Canal water	-2993.854	-3.332	0.001
Cultivated area	0.821	4.946	0.000

The results illustrate that a one degree rise in minimum temperature increases wheat yield by approximately 59.7 units indicating adaptive warming benefits. Fertilizer usage significantly enhances yields highlighting the importance of input intensity as it is highly significant. Cultivated area for wheat production contributes positively to the production, underscoring land expansion's role. Whereas, canal water available for wheat production negatively affects productivity. As water is required at certain time in the cropping season. If water is available at harvesting time, this will negatively affect the crop.

Table 4.7: Rice production in central Punjab

Variable	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Rainfall	-0.074	-0.655	0.513
Maximum temperature	-6.863	-1.599	0.113
Minimum temperature	25.762	5.668	0.000
Fertilizer use	223.187	3.001	0.003
Canal water	-406.248	-1.416	0.161
Cultivated area	0.821	6.526	0.000

The results show that a one degree increase in minimum temperature increases rice yield by approximately 25.7 units, indicating adaptive warming benefits. Use of fertilizers significantly enhances rice yields highlighting the importance of input intensity as it is highly significant. Cultivated area for rice production in central Punjab contributes positively to the production, underscoring land expansion's role. Whereas, canal water available for wheat production negatively affects productivity. As water is required at certain time in the cropping season. If water

Table 4.8: Maize production in central Punjab

Variable	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Rainfall	0.154	0.979	0.330
Maximum temperature	-11.783	-3.268	0.001
Minimum temperature	25.336	7.889	0.000
Fertilizer use	39.893	5.626	0.000
Canal water	62.266	2.239	0.027
Cultivated area	2.843	7.473	0.000

The results in the table above show that rainfall variation in the Districts Lahore,

Maximum temperature and rainfall do not significantly impact wheat yield in the central region. This table shows a comprehensive assessment of the impact of climate variation on wheat production in Punjab.

3.4.2.2 Rice production model

The Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square regression results for rice production indicate that minimum temperature, fertilizer usage, and cultivated area for rice, are strong positive drivers, while rainfall and maximum temperature remain insignificant. These findings reflect the region's reliance on controlled irrigation rather than natural precipitation.

is available at harvesting time, this will negatively affect the crop. Maximum temperature and rainfall do not significantly impact rice yield in the central region.

3.4.2.3 Maize production model

The Fully Modified Ordinary Least Square regression results for maize production indicate that rainfall, minimum temperature, fertilizer usage, and cultivated area for maize, are strong positive drivers, while maximum temperature remain insignificant.

Faisalabad and Sialkot play a significant role in determining maize yield in this model. The coefficient of maximum temperature -11.783 is negative and large which indicates highly significant negative impact on maize yield. Rising maximum temperatures are detrimental for maize yield. The coefficient of Minimum Temperature is positive and highly significant. A one

degree rise in minimum temperature will increase maize yield. Use of fertilizer and canal water have positive significant effect on maize yield, showing that these inputs are key drivers of productivity, showing input intensification is effective.

3.2.3 South Punjab

South Punjab is the irrigated region. Table 4.9: Wheat production in south Punjab

Variable	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Rainfall	-1.97	-2.675	0.009
Maximum temperature	-35.640	-3.882	0.002
Minimum temperature	52.651	4.747	0.000
Fertilizer use	-484.437	-1.783	0.078
Canal water	-1872.42	-1.476	0.144
Cultivated area	1.787	11.281	0.000

Rainfall has a significant negative effect which shows excessive rainfall is harmful for wheat yield in this region. Minimum temperature has a strong positive effect on wheat yield whereas maximum temperature exerts a strong negative and highly significant effect, which confirms that high heat stress reduces wheat yield. Canal water has negative and insignificant effect, due to inefficiencies in irrigation water. Fertilizer usage has negative but significant effect possibly due to overuse or imbalance of fertilizer application.

Table 4.10: Rice production in south Punjab

Variable	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Rainfall	0.516	3.443	0.000
Maximum temperature	0.283	0.148	0.882
Minimum temperature	0.224	0.104	0.917

agricultural land, dominated by cotton, wheat, rice, sugarcane and mangoes. This region is part of the Indus Basin irrigated zone and highly dependent on canal water from Sutlej, Chenab and Indus River. It is highly vulnerable to climate induced events like floods, water shortage and extreme temperatures. While it plays an important role in exports of Pakistan. In this research study three districts Bahawalnagar, Multan and Bahawalpur were selected for analysis of crop production.

3.2.3.1 Wheat production model

Wheat production model used FMOLS technique to estimate production in South Punjab. This model shows diverse climate and input influences.

Results show that in South Punjab wheat production is highly sensitive to temperature extremes and rainfall patterns in Punjab.

3.2.3.2 Rice production model

Rice production in south Punjab is mainly depending on rainfall water, temperature variation, fertilizers usage, canal water and land available for cultivation. FMOLS technique was used to estimate relationship between rice production and inputs. Results are presented below:

Fertilizer use	37.251	5.811	0.000
Canal water	-22.128	-1.039	0.301
Cultivated area	1.787	11.281	0.000

Results in the table 4.10 above show that Rainfall has positive and highly significant effect on rice production which underlines rice’s dependency on abundant water. Maximum temperature has positive but insignificant effect on rice production. Similarly, minimum temperature has also positive and insignificant effect which shows weak influence of temperature extremes on rice. Fertilizer usage is highly significant and has positive effect on rice yield. Canal water has negative but insignificant effect on rice yield, possibly due to in appropriate management or distribution of water.

Table 4.11: Cotton production in south Punjab

Variable	Coefficient	T-statistic	P-value
Rainfall	-6.353062	-3.428937	0.0010
Maximum temperature	-54.82389	-2.551035	0.0126
Minimum temperature	60.69935	2.505445	0.0142
Fertilizer use	47.77033	0.243053	0.8086
Canal water	-50.20408	-0.019683	0.9843
Cultivated area	2.602992	6.075390	0.0000

Results in the table 4.11 above highlights climate sensitivity and land importance. Rainfall in South Punjab has negative effect on cotton yield which shows excessive rain damages crop growth and fiber quality. Maximum Temperature has a significant negative impact on cotton yield which shows that cotton crop is vulnerable to heat stress. Whereas, minimum temperature has positive and significant effect on cotton yield. Fertilizer use has positive but insignificant effect on cotton production, which indicates

Cultivated area available for the production of rice has strongest positive effect on rice yield showing land expansion can boost rice yield in this region.

3.2.3.3 Cotton production model

Cotton production in South Punjab is mainly depending on rainfall water, fertilizer usage, canal water available, cultivated area and temperature variation. For analysis of the data, FMOLS regression is used and long-run relationship b/w inputs and cotton production has been developed. Results of the model are presented below:

weak responsiveness to fertilizer usage. Canal water is also statistically insignificant and has negative effect on cotton production. Cultivated area available for cotton production shows a strong positive effect, showing land expansion is key driver to enhance cotton yield. Overall, cotton production is highly climate sensitive, with rainfall and temperature variation being harmful.

Conclusion

The results of this study demonstrate that climate change is exerting a profound influence on Pakistan's temperature regime, rainfall variability, glacier melt, river flows, and agricultural productivity. Long term temperature data (1901-2020) show a persistent warming trend, consistent with global climate assessments, while rainfall patterns have become increasingly erratic. These climatic changes are directly affecting the hydrology of Pakistan's major river systems, where glacier-fed flows during the Kharif season fluctuate sharply due to rising temperatures, and Rabi flows remain low due to winter snow accumulation. This mismatch between water availability and agricultural requirements amplifies production risks for farmers.

The FMOLS results across North, Central, and South Punjab reveal region-specific climate vulnerabilities: wheat production is highly sensitive to maximum temperature increases; rice is strongly dependent on rainfall and cultivated area; cotton and maize show significant yield reductions under heat stress. Fertilizer use and cultivated area consistently enhance yields in most regions, yet climate-related factors especially maximum temperature and rainfall extreme remain dominant drivers of agricultural outcomes. The evidence confirms that Punjab's agricultural sector is increasingly climate-constrained, and the impacts are intensifying over time.

These findings collectively indicate that climate change poses a significant threat to crop yields, food security, and rural livelihoods in Punjab. Without targeted adaptation, climate-induced losses will continue to escalate, threatening long-term agricultural sustainability.

Policy Implications:

The results underscore the need for targeted climate adaptation measures to stabilize agricultural productivity in Punjab. Policy priorities should include the deployment of climate resilient crop varieties, optimization of irrigation scheduling through high-

efficiency water systems and enhanced hydrometeorological monitoring to support data-driven decision making. Strengthening water governance within the Indus Basin, improving input-use efficiency particularly fertilizers and expanding climate advisory services are essential to mitigate yield losses. These interventions must be institutionalized within existing frameworks such as the Pakistan Climate Change Policy (2021) and National Water Policy (2018) to ensure long-term agricultural resilience and food security.

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